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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

“YASHIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH” TIZIMINING TARKIBI VA AMAL QILISH XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada global miqyosda “yashil iqtisodiyot”ga o‘tishning zaruriyati va ushbu jarayonni moliyalashtirish mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, “yashil moliyalashtirish” tushunchasining mohiyati, shakllanish bosqichlari va xalqaro amaliyotda qo‘llanilayotgan moliyaviy vositalar ko‘rib chiqilgan. Yashil iqtisodiyotning asosiy tarmoqlari — qayta tiklanadigan energiya, ekologik transport, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash, resurslarni tejovchi texnologiyalar — moliyaviy yondashuvlar bilan uzviy bog‘liq ekanligi asoslab berilgan. Shuningdek, yashil moliyalashtirishda uchraydigan risklar, investitsiyaviy jozibadorlikni oshirish usullari, “yashil obligatsiyalar”ning afzalliklari va davlatning roli tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, yashil moliyalashtirish, ekologik investitsiyalar, qayta tiklanadigan energiya, yashil obligatsiyalar.

So‘nggi yillarda global miqyosda “yashil iqtisodiyot”ga o‘tish jarayoni insoniyat oldida turgan ekologik, iqtisodiy va energetik muammolarga kompleks yondashuv zaruriyatidan kelib chiqmoqda. Bu o‘zgarishlar uzoq muddatli strategik qarorlar, texnologik transformatsiyalar va katta hajmdagi investitsiyalarni talab etadi. Xususan, Xalqaro energetika agentligi hisob-kitoblariga ko‘ra, 2050-yilgacha CO₂ gazining global miqdorini ikki baravarga kamaytirish uchun dunyo yalpi ichki mahsulotining kamida 1–2,5 foizi miqdorida qo‘shimcha sarmoya kiritilishi lozim.

Yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tishdagi asosiy omillardan biri bu — barqaror moliyaviy infratuzilmani shakllantirishdir. Ayni jihat “yashil moliya” tushunchasini ilgari suradi. Hozirgi kunda bu atama yagona aniqlik kasb etmagan bo‘lsa-da, umumiy nuqtai nazardan ekologik barqarorlikni ta‘minlaydigan loyihalarni moliyalashtirishga xizmat qiluvchi barcha moliyaviy vositalarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Bunga energiya samaradorligi yuqori bo‘lgan texnologiyalar, past uglerodli transport turlari, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash tizimlari va boshqa ekologik loyihalarni qo‘llab-quvvatlovchi investitsiyalar kiradi.

“Yashil moliya” atamasi ilk bor 1992-yilda iqtisodchi Richard Sandor tomonidan Kolumbiya universitetida taqdim etilgan bo‘lsa, keyinchalik bu tushuncha

ekologik barqarorlik konsepsiyasining asosiy moliyaviy ustuniga aylana boshladi. Shu sohada olib borilgan yirik tadqiqotlardan biri — Stenford universiteti professori Gletchen Deylning “Yangi tabiat iqtisodiyoti” asaridir. U yashil iqtisodiyotni moliyaviy jihatdan barqaror rivojlantirish usullarini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan.

Karl Burkat tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan modelga ko‘ra, yashil iqtisodiyot quyidagi asosiy tarmoqlarni qamrab oladi: qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalari, ekologik toza transport, yashil qurilish, suv resurslarini tejash va boshqarish, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash, yer unumdorligini oshirish va organik qishloq xo‘jaligi.

Har bir sohaning rivojlanish bosqichi o‘ziga xos moliyaviy yondashuv va manbalarni talab qiladi. Shu bois, yashil moliyalashtirish bo‘yicha xalqaro yondashuvlar ham turlicha shakllangan. Misol uchun, Bloomberg New Energy Finance kompaniyasi vakillari bu tushunchani kengroq talqin qilib, uni ekologik yo‘nalishdagi barcha moliyaviy mexanizmlarni qamrab oluvchi vosita sifatida ko‘rsatadi.

Moliyaviy sektorda yashil moliyalashtirish jarayoniga banklar, sug‘urta kompaniyalari, investitsiya fondlari, xalqaro donorlar faol jalb etilmoqda. PricewaterhouseCoopers ekspertlari fikricha, yashil kreditlar bank tizimining ekologik mas‘uliyatli yondashuvini ifodalaydi va ushbu tamoyillar kredit ajratishning barcha bosqichlarida namoyon bo‘ladi. Xalqaro moliya korporatsiyasi esa yashil moliyalashtirishni atrof-muhitga salbiy ta‘sirni kamaytirishga xizmat qiluvchi keng ko‘lamli loyihalarni to‘plam sifatida talqin qiladi.

“Yashil” loyihalarni moliyalashtirishda duch kelinayotgan asosiy muammo — ularning yuqori risklilik darajasidir. Bu omil, ayniqsa, xususiy investorlar tomonidan kapital kiritish qarorlarini qabul qilishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Texnologik yangiliklarning beqarorligi, investitsiyani qoplash muddati uzoqligi va ekologik infratuzilmaning rivojlanmaganligi sababli ko‘plab investorlar ushbu yo‘nalishga ehtiyotkorlik bilan yondashadi.

Shunga qaramay, jahonda “yashil iqtisodiyot”ni moliyalashtirishning turli manbalari shakllanmoqda. Jumladan:

- Davlat byudjeti mablag‘lari;
- Xalqaro moliya institutlari grant va kreditlari (masalan, Jahon banki, Yevropa tiklanish va taraqqiyot banki, Xalqaro moliya korporatsiyasi);
- Xususiy sektor investitsiyalari (ichki va tashqi kapital ishtiroki).

Yashil moliyalashtirishning eng samarali vositalaridan biri — bu “yashil obligatsiyalar” hisoblanadi. Ular dastlab Yevropa investitsiya banki tomonidan chiqarilgan bo‘lib, keyinchalik “iqlim obligatsiyalari” nomi ostida keng tarqaldi. Bu qimmatbaho qog‘ozlar orqali jalb qilingan mablag‘lar faqat ekologik loyihalarga yo‘naltiriladi. 2008-yilda Jahon banki bu obligatsiyalarni rasmiy ravishda “green bonds” sifatida nomlab, ularni ekologik mezonlarga asoslangan tahlil asosida ishlab chiqdi.

Yashil obligatsiyalar orqali energiya samaradorligini oshirish, qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalariga o‘tish, chiqindilarni kamaytirish kabi maqsadlar moliyaviy jihatdan qo‘llab-quvvatlanmoqda. Xususan, 2018-yilga kelib global

miqyosda bunday yo‘nalishdagi sarmoyalar hajmi 2010-yilga nisbatan 55 foizga oshgan.

Bu jarayonlarda davlat roli ham nihoyatda muhim. Hukumatlar imtiyozli soliq siyosati, subsidiyalar, kafolat mexanizmlari va qonunchilik bazasi orqali yashil investitsiyalar uchun qulay muhit yaratishi zarur. Shuningdek, jamoatchilik ongini oshirish, atrof-muhitga mas‘uliyatli munosabatni shakllantirish va ekologik texnologiyalarni ommalashtirish orqali yashil iqtisodiyotning barqaror rivojlanishiga erishiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, yashil iqtisodiyot insoniyatning ekologik muammolarga berayotgan javobi bo‘lib, bu yo‘nalishda moliyalashtirish mexanizmlari hal qiluvchi rol o‘ynaydi. Yashil moliyalashtirish orqali iqtisodiy o‘shish, ijtimoiy farovonlik va ekologik xavfsizlik bir vaqtda ta‘minlanishi mumkin. Shu bois, global darajada barqaror iqtisodiy taraqqiyotga erishish uchun yashil moliya vositalari strategik ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

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